

INTERRELATIONSHIP OF SEMANTIC PARALLELISMS IN TURKIC AND EUROPEAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article examines the interrelationship of semantic parallelisms in Turkic and European languages. Despite belonging to different language families, these languages exhibit both common principles and distinctive features of semantic parallelism. Semantic parallelism plays a significant role, particularly in poetry, folklore, and literary texts. The study analyzes how rhythmic-syntactic parallelism manifests in Turkic languages and how syntactic and lexical parallelisms appear in European languages. Additionally, the relationship of this phenomenon with historical, cultural, and linguistic factors is discussed.*

Keywords: *Semantic parallelism, Turkic languages, European languages, rhythmic-syntactic parallelism, folklore, artistic speech, linguistic typology, grammar, syntax, cultural correlation.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada turkiy va Yevropa tillarida semantik parallelizmlarning o‘zaro aloqadorligi tahlil qilinadi. Turli tillar oilalariga mansub bo‘lishiga qaramay, bu tillarda semantik parallelizmning umumiy tamoyillari va o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari mavjud. Semantik parallelizm, ayniqsa, she‘riyat, xalq og‘zaki ijodi va badiiy matnlarda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Tadqiqotda turkiy tillarda ritmik-sintaktik parallelizmning qanday namoyon bo‘lishi hamda Yevropa tillarida sintaktik va leksik parallelizmlarning qo‘llanilishi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, ushbu hodisaning tarixiy, madaniy va lingvistik omillar bilan bog‘liqligi muhokama qilinadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Semantik parallelizm, turkiy tillar, Yevropa tillari, ritmik-sintaktik parallelizm, xalq og‘zaki ijodi, badiiy nutq, lingvistik tipologiya, grammatika, sintaksis, madaniy bog‘liqlik.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматривается взаимосвязь семантических параллелизмов в тюркских и европейских языках. Несмотря на принадлежность к разным языковым семьям, эти языки демонстрируют как общие принципы, так и уникальные особенности семантического параллелизма. Семантический параллелизм играет значительную роль, особенно в поэзии, фольклоре и литературных текстах. В исследовании анализируется, как ритмико-синтаксический параллелизм проявляется в тюркских языках, а также как синтаксические и лексические параллелизмы представлены в европейских языках. Кроме того, обсуждается связь этого явления с историческими, культурными и лингвистическими факторами.*

Ключевые слова: *Семантический параллелизм, тюркские языки, европейские языки, ритмико-синтаксический параллелизм, фольклор, художественная речь, лингвистическая типология, грамматика, синтаксис, культурная взаимосвязь.*

Introduction: Semantic parallelism refers to the phenomenon in which words, phrases, or grammatical structures with identical or similar meanings are repeated across different languages. This phenomenon is widely observed in folklore, poetry, and literary texts. Although Turkic and European languages belong to different genealogical groups, they share both similarities and differences in their semantic structures. Turkic languages, including Uzbek,

Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Turkish, and others, often exhibit semantic parallelism in a rhythmic-syntactic form. This stylistic device is frequently used in poetic texts, epic works, and oral folk traditions. For instance, V.M.Zhirmunsky emphasized that rhythmic-syntactic parallelism is a fundamental structural technique in the epic narratives of Turkic peoples. In European languages, parallelisms often manifest as syntactic or lexical stylistic devices. For example, English phrases like *Easy come, easy go* and German expressions such as *Wie gewonnen, so zerronnen* serve as prominent examples of syntactic parallelism. This article explores how semantic parallelisms have formed in Turkic and European languages, their role in linguistic systems, and their connections with cultural factors.

Main discussion: The interrelation of semantic parallelisms in Turkic and European languages is one of the intriguing and complex issues in linguistics. Despite their distinct language families, these languages exhibit both similarities and differences in their semantic structures. Semantic parallelism refers to the repetition or contrast of words, phrases, or grammatical structures with identical or similar meanings within speech. This phenomenon is widely utilized in both Turkic and European languages, yet its application and meaning vary due to cultural, historical, and linguistic factors. Turkic languages, particularly Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, and Turkish, share close interrelations. Semantic parallelism in these languages frequently appears in poetic texts, folklore, and speech styles. In Turkic languages, ideas are often reiterated or contrasted through parallel structures, enhancing the artistic and emotional impact of speech. For instance, in Uzbek poetry, expressions like *tears of the eyes – sorrows of the heart* exemplify semantic parallelism. Such phrases deeply convey human emotions and inner states. Renowned scholar V.M.Zhirmunsky studied rhythmic-syntactic parallelism as a key structural technique in Turkic epic narratives, highlighting its regulatory role in the formation and structure of ancient Turkic folk poetry. According to the scholar, the alternation of poetic and prose sections, each exhibiting rhythmic segmentation through syntactic parallelism, is a traditional style of Turkic epic poetry.[1] He asserted that the most emotionally expressive thoughts are maximally emphasized through symmetrically structured sentences. Furthermore, he noted the precise preservation of syntactic parallelism, where two parallel grammatical structures are identically organized.

Although this literary phenomenon is not entirely identical to the highly developed rhythmic-syntactic parallelism found in folklore, it undeniably shares a connection. Describing specific instances of literary parallelism is crucial, as it serves as a vital artistic tool in not only Chagatai literature but also, as L.Yu.Tugusheva noted, in ancient Uyghur literature. This parallelism ensures rhythmic segmentation, thereby shaping the unique rhythm of prose—a feature that merits special attention. Below, we examine how syntactic parallelism manifests in both phrases and sentence structures. The Baburnama, written at the turn of the 15th and 16th centuries, is an extensive prose work that encompasses a vast artistic period, covering Babur’s life from the age of twelve, when he ascended the throne of Andijan, to his reign as the founder of the Mughal Empire in India. The work’s artistic space is equally vast, including Transoxiana, Iran, Afghanistan, and India. At first glance, the Baburnama appears to be a simple and direct narrative of the author's life events, contemporary realities, and environmental descriptions. Babur seemingly does not embellish his text excessively; he even frequently deviates from literary syntactic norms, as evidenced by the frequent ellipses of compound predicates, inversions, and other features. However, in reality, this is a meticulously crafted prose, shaped primarily by medieval literary etiquette. According to D.M.Likhachyov, depictions in Old Russian literature were dictated by literary etiquette, which consisted of *the etiquette of world*

order, the etiquette of behavior, and the etiquette of words.[2] The principle of arbitrariness and conventionality of linguistic signs is a widely applied concept in linguistics. However, the linguistic system retains traces of its original motivation throughout its historical development, making this phenomenon highly relevant in explaining semantic parallelism across different languages. One of the founders of semiotics, C.S.Peirce, classified linguistic signs into three types: iconic signs, indices, and symbols. This classification is applicable for analyzing different forms of semantic parallelism in linguistic systems. For instance, iconic signs reflect the formation of semantic parallelism based on resemblance, while indices explain the existence of the same phenomenon in different languages through real connections or historical contact. Symbols, on the other hand, may generate semantic parallelism through conventional associations.

Peirce's classification serves as a useful analytical tool in studying semantic parallelism in Turkic and European languages, as linguistic signs often possess a combination of these three characteristics, with one prevailing feature determining their classification.[3] One of the essential factors in the formation of semantic parallelism is the content of the sentence and the semantic correlation of linguistic units within the language system. All the aforementioned semantic elements, particularly verb forms with affixal expressions, can only be precisely defined through reference to the communicative act and orientation towards the speaker. In other words, these semantic units are formed depending on the speaker's position, thereby reflecting the relationship of the conveyed information to reality. I.I.Revzin referred to such meanings as communicative meanings, emphasizing that they exist solely within the act of communication.[4] Another critical aspect of semantic parallelism is the relationship between reality and irreality (conditionals, desires, probabilities) and their correlation with the time axis. Due to the continuous and relative nature of reality, it is difficult to clearly distinguish between factual events and modal meanings such as necessity, obligation, and possibility in verb forms. V.Z.Panfilov argued that the modal meanings of desire, obligation, and demand, expressed in Turkic verb forms, should not be considered entirely unreal.[5] According to the scholar, *Why should the meanings of desire, obligation, and demand be regarded as unreal, i.e., non-existent, when the very existence of these conditions is being stated?* This principle plays a significant role in understanding semantic parallelism between Turkic and European languages.

Conclusion: The presence of semantic parallelisms in Turkic and European languages is shaped by their historical, cultural, and linguistic characteristics. In Turkic languages, parallelisms mainly appear in rhythmic-syntactic forms, while in European languages, they predominantly manifest as syntactic and lexical devices. These structures are extensively used in poetry, folklore, and literary texts, enhancing both the logical and emotional impact of speech. The findings indicate that analyzing semantic parallelisms is crucial for understanding linguistic typology and cultural interrelations. In Turkic languages, this phenomenon is primarily found in oral traditions and artistic speech, whereas in European languages, it serves as a logical structuring tool. This research provides valuable insights into linguistic universals and distinctions, contributing to a broader understanding of language relationships and their cognitive implications.

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